

Development of a Vegetation Searching System

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Abstract : This paper describes the development of a Vegetation Searching System based on Web Application in case of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. The model was developed by PHP, JavaScript, and MySQL database system and it was designed to support searching endemic and rare species of tree on web site. We describe the design methods and functional components of this prototype. To evaluate the system performance, questionnaires for system usability and Black Box Testing were used to measure expert and user satisfaction. The results were satisfactory as followed: Means for experts and users were 4.3 and 4.5, and standard deviation for experts and users were 0.61 and 0.73 respectively. Further analysis showed that the quality of plant searching web site was also at a good level as well.

Keywords : endemic species, vegetation, web-based system, black box testing, Thailand

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